

NEAR SURFACE MEASUREMENTS WITH A DOPPLER CURRENT PROFILER

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the ability of the RD Instruments 1200 kHz Doppler Current Profiler to measure currents in the near surface layer. Data will be presented from tests conducted at the Navy's David Taylor Research Center where an RD system was mounted on a bottom sled in an upward looking mode. The sled was towed by a carriage at precise speeds in a test basin with and without waves.

Data shows mean flow errors with and without waves in all bins to the surface. Data was also sampled at sufficient speed to look at wave particle velocities. An evaluation of that data is presented and also an evaluation of sidelobe effects and sidelobe deflection techniques to obtain undistorted measurements.

INTRODUCTION

Doppler current profilers (DCP) use narrow, directional acoustic beams as the energy source for current measurement[1]. The backscattered acoustic energy from a cloud of particles in the water column is analyzed to determine the Doppler shift due to the relative movement of those particles. The beamwidth and side lobe energy levels are important aspects of DCP performance. Beamwidth is characterized at the -3 dB level and is measured in degrees of arc. A typical RD 1200 kHz transducer has a beamwidth of 1.4 degrees. The main beam lobe contains most of the energy emitted. However, other transducer characteristics such as size and vibration modes generate beam sidelobes. These sidelobes are typically -40 dB below the main lobe [fig. 1]. The characteristics of these beams are significant in determining near surface and near bottom measurement accuracy.

The sidelobe energy at 30 degrees from the main beam, with a typical 30 degree transducer angle, points directly toward the surface or bottom. The echo return from a hard surface is much larger than from particles in the water. Even with 2-way (transmit and receive) energy levels down 80 dB, the return signal level is strong enough to contaminate measurements. This energy is received at the same time as the energy from 85% of the profiling range [fig. 2].

Contamination from sidelobes has the effect of biasing the velocity measurement towards zero. The worst case condition is a mirror surface that would reflect all the energy back towards the receiver. In this case the surface is not moving and therefore does not Doppler shift the signal. The bias mechanism is thought to result from this large signal indicating no relative velocity. In actual in-situ conditions, the results are dependant on sea surface conditions. The angle of reflection with the surface wave is constantly changing. This means that the amount of backscattered energy received is varying and the surface is moving creating a Doppler shift in the signal. The footprint of the beam at the surface and wavelength of the signal may also have an effect. In a downward looking mode, contamination from bottom echoes is a function of bottom characteristics. In a moving vessel the results may also be unpredictable.

Figure 1. Typical ADCP beam pattern.

RD Instruments recommends that you do not use measurement acquired beyond 85% of the range when surface or bottom reflections are present.

EXPERIMENT DESIGN

In an effort to study and quantify the near surface measurement accuracy a series of tests were designed using the David Taylor Research Center towing basin. This facility has been used previously to investigate Doppler profiler accuracies [2]. RD 1200 kHz and 600 kHz systems have successfully been calibrated in the first 4

bins in a downward looking mode. During those tests it had been observed that measurements were biased low in bin 5. It was concluded that sidelobe returns from the concrete basin bottom biased the measurements at 85% of the range. It was also noted that the next bin, bin 6, was not contaminated.

Figure 2. ADCP configuration of 1 measurement plane in the DTRC tow basin (not to scale).

A bottom sled was used to mount a 1200 kHz profiler with a right angle head adapter in an upward looking mode. The sled was guided by a drainage trough that ran the length of the basin. It was towed from the carriage using 2 tow lines for stability. One end of the tow basin contains a pneumatic wave maker. Maximum amplitude waves of 1 meter peak to peak are possible at a 3 second period. An acoustic wave gage was mounted on the carriage [fig. 3 & 4] to measure wave height simultaneously with current data.

Figure 3. DTRC ADCP wave study test configuration towing east.

The profiler was modified by RD Instruments with firmware changes to allow communications at 38.4 Kbaud. This allowed us to acquire single ping ensembles from the profiler at the rate of 5 per second. Single ping ensembles have an estimated precision of 9.6 cm/s. The bin length and pulse length were set to 1 meter; blanking to 0.5 meter. Tests were conducted with beams 3 and 4 aligned in the towing direction and beams 1 and 2 cross channel.

Figure 4. DTRC ADCP wave study test configuration towing west.

A PC-based data acquisition system acquired binary data from the profiler in beam coordinates. Simultaneous inputs from the tow carriage speed readout and wave gage were recorded.

Tests were conducted at a variety of tow speeds and surface wave conditions. In all cases pulverized limestone was added to the basin water to keep echo amplitude above 60 dB in bin 1 [2]. The system was calibrated by towing at speeds from a tow carriage threshold of 2 cm/s up to 100 cm/s. Zero data was taken at the beginning and end of each test run. A minimum of 200 single ping ensembles was acquired for each test condition.

SIDELobe Baffles

It has been theorized that acoustic sidelobes could be deflected and/or absorbed so that they become impotent. The idea is to develop a device that would allow the main beam to progress undisturbed but restrict the propagation of the sidelobes. Experiments have been conducted by NOAA during field tests with prototype baffles having encouraging results [3][4]. These tests were conducted in the early 1980's with an AMETEK Straza 300 kHz system. The device consisted of a cone shaped baffle that was placed between the beams. Sidelobes would strike the baffle and be reflected in a horizontal direction. Stray acoustic energy coming from the surface would be reflected and/or absorbed by the top surface of the baffle.

A crude cone shaped baffle was fabricated for the DTRC tests. It was foam filled and attached to threaded rod placed in the transducer head attachment bolt holes. The angle and placement of the baffle was such as to allow the main beam to progress undisturbed. However, it would block energy at angles greater than 5 degrees from the main lobe. Foam extensions were fabricated to increase the baffle size [photo 1]. Calibrations were conducted with the baffle in place and no surface waves to determine the baffles effects. Test were repeated with surface waves.

Photo 1. ADCP in upward looking position with large baffle.

RD Instruments began experimenting with baffle design in 1989 based on the results of these tests. RD Instruments conducted beam pattern tests on a 1200 kHz system with a baffle showing marked reduction in sidelobe energy [fig. 5]. In January of 1990 tests were conducted with an RD designed baffle using a 1200 kHz system in a downward looking mode [photo 2]. The system was calibrated without the baffle and tests repeated with the baffle. The concrete basin floor provided an ideal reflecting surface for study of sidelobe contamination.

Figure 5. ADCP beam pattern with baffle attached.

EXPERIMENT RESULTS

The calibration results were typical for a 1200 kHz system [2]. Data was analyzed on a beam basis because of the preferential orientation of the profiler. The radial velocity component was used for each of beams 3 and 4. The carriage velocity in the plane of the beams was computed, assuming no vertical component. The following results are the average of 200 ensembles of 1 ping each, 40 seconds

of data, for each test condition. No flow conditions showed a positive 1 to 2 cm/s bias in all beams and bins. Tow speeds of up to 100 cm/s contained beam errors of within ± 2 cm/s in the first 3 bins. Bin 1 had occasionally higher errors of up to 4 cm/s. Bin 4 consistently had negative errors of from 4 to 10 cm/s. Bin 4 is estimated to be at 85% of the range and receives the sidelobe energy. Bin 5 returned to a normal range of errors [fig. 6].

Photo 2. ADCP with small baffle attached when towed from the DTRC carriage in a downward looking position.

Data was taken under identical tow carriage speeds as the calibration but with surface waves. The first wave conditions were small ripples of approximately 4 centimeters RMS. The second condition was 20 centimeter RMS waves with a 3 second period. The small wave results were not much different from the no wave conditions. Bin 4 still showed a large negative bias from the sidelobes [fig. 6]. The large waves, however, showed a marked improvement in the bin 4 bias. Although the data were still negatively biased, the worst case errors were at 4 cm/s [fig. 6]. Data from the other bins showed that wave particle velocities in the water column had no adverse effect on the ability to determine mean flow [fig. 6]. Tows into and away from the waves had the apparent effect of changing the wave frequency. However, no noticeable effect in profiler performance was noted.

Baffle test showed no adverse effects on profiler performance [fig. 7]. The results in bin 4 were dependant on the size of the baffle. The small baffle did improve the performance in bin 4. However, the larger size baffle showed marked improvement. Errors in bin 4 were reduced to normal system errors showing no signs of the negative bias. Bins 1 showed a slight negative bias when compared to the no cone data.

A similar baffle test was conducted on a 1200 kHz system towed from the carriage in a downward looking mode. This baffle was a prototype made by

RD Instruments. Again, the results showed a marked improvement in the bin receiving the sidelobe energy.

no significant information was portrayed by the echo amplitude. It was noted, however, that echo amplitude increased in bins 4 and 5 under surface wave conditions.

Figure 6. DTRC towed sled wave tests without baffle under different wave conditions.

Wave particle velocities along the beams were measured and analyzed. The frequency content of the wave spectra was reproduced accurately in the profiler data [fig. 8]. Phase differences in the beams were apparent due to beam spreading. Wall reflections of wave energy also reproduced velocities in the cross channel beams.

Echo amplitude was analyzed for significant information regarding profiler performance. It had been discovered in previous tests that the echo amplitude in bin 1 should be above 60 dB for optimum performance. Pulverized limestone addition to the basin provided sufficient scatterers. In general,

Figure 7. DTRC towed sled test with different baffle sizes, no waves.

SUMMARY

The 1200 kHz Doppler current profiler has demonstrated the ability to accurately measure mean currents in a dynamic wave induced flow field. It has also been shown that sidelobes bias the measurements at 85% of the range when bottom or surface constraints are present. This bias is unpredictable based on bottom or surface roughness. Sidelobe bias can be eliminated with a properly designed baffle system. We have also demonstrated the profilers ability to measure wave particle velocities with a properly configured system.

Figure 8. Energy content of each bin for beams 3 and 4, with and without baffle. Energy in the wave height spectrum is included to show frequency of the waves and correlation to particle velocity frequency.

[4] G.F. Appell, T.N. Merc, J.J. Sprenke, D.R. Schmidt, "An Intercomparison of Two Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers," Proceedings of OCEANS'85, November 1985.

Further research needs to be performed on baffle design. Field tests need to be conducted and the baffle effects with lower frequency profilers need study.

REFERENCES

[1] "Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers Principles of Operation: A Practical Primer," RD Instruments, January 1989.

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[3] G.F. Appell, "A Real-Time Current Measurement System," Sea Technology, Vol. 25, No. 2, February 1984.